

EFFECT OF ADDITIVES (SPICES) ON THE ORGANOLEPTIC CHARACTERISTICS OF BEEF, CHICKEN AND GOAT MEATS CONSUMED IN NIGERIA

Eluyode O.S and Akpa O.L

Department of General Studies, Federal College of Agriculture, Akure 340001, Ondo State, Nigeria.

ABSTRACTS

The aim of this study was to determine the Nigerian consumer descriptive panel ratings for meats (goat, beef and chicken) cooked with nine different spices. Twenty (n = 20) member panel tasted and rated on a nine-point hedonic scale their degree of liking for the samples varying in added spices. Subjects were asked to complete a questioner about consumption of the meat samples. Degree of liking differed significantly ($p > 0.05$) among samples and the samples best liked was that cooked with magi cube, which was reported to contain active ingredients like sodium chloride and monosodium glutamate. The manufactures of this cube reported the presence of vegetable fat, starch and spices in them. These are believed to have released more flavour components, which might have contributed to the improved meet.

KEYWORDS: additives, spices, meat, food condiment, Akure, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Food additives are any substance that become part of a food product or that otherwise affect the characteristics of any food, directly or indirectly through producing, processing, treating, packaging, transporting, or storing. Some 2,800 substances are intentionally added to foods, whereas 10,000 other compounds find their way into the foods during processing, packaging or storage (Nieman *et al* 1992).

The role of food additives has become more prominent in recent years due to the changes that have occurred in peoples' life-style. Food additives are classified as:

1. Nutrients – Their functions are meat to enrich (replace vitamins and minerals lost in processing) or fortify to add nutrients that may be lacking in the diet.
2. Preservatives (Antimicrobials)- They prevent food spoilage from microorganisms.
3. Preservatives (Antioxidants)- They delay or prevent undesirable changes in colour, flavours, or texture – enzymatic oxidation or discoloration due to oxidation, delay or prevent rancidity in food with unstable oils.
4. Emulsifiers – Helps to evenly distribute tiny particles of one liquid into another eg oil and water, modify surface tension of liquid to establish a uniform dispersion or emulsion, improve homogeneity, consistency, stability and texture.
5. Stabilizers, thickeners, texturizers-They impact body, improve consistency, texture, stabilize emulsions, affect appearance/mouth feel of the food, many are natural carbohydrate which absorb water in the food.
6. Leavening agents-Their functions affect cooking results, texture and increase volume, also some flaw our effects.
7. pH control agents- Their functions control acidity or alkalinity, can affect texture, taste and wholesomeness.
8. Humectants in their own case retain moisture
9. Maturing and bleaching agents, dough conditioner accelerate the aging process to develop the gluten characteristics of flour, improve baking qualities
10. Anticracking agents – Help keep salts and powders free flavouring, prevent craking, humping or clustering of a finely powdered or crystalline substance.

11. Flavour enhancers – They function as substances with supplements, magnify or modify the original taste and /or aroma of a food-without imparting a characteristic taste or aroma of its own.
12. Flavours makes foods taste better, improve natural flavour, restore flavours lost in processing.
13. Sweeteners make the aroma or taste of a food more agreeable or pleasurable (Wardlaw, 1999)

Table 1: spices used for the study

S/N	Name of seasonings			Texture after grinding
	Common Name	Botanical Name	Local Name	
1	Ginger	<i>Zingiber officinal</i>	-	sticky
2	Garlic	<i>Allium spp</i>	-	pastry
3	Pole	-	Mnkpuru ^a	coarse
4	African nutmeg	<i>Monodora mysritica</i>	-	Rough powder
5	Maggi cube	-	-	powdery
6	-	-	Ohiha ^a	coarse
7	-	-	Oziza ^a	coarse
8	Locust bean	<i>Parkia biglobosa</i>	Iru ^b	sticky
9	-	-	Ewuru ^a	coarse

a- Igbo b- Yoruba

Table 2: Sensory Evaluation results of samples analysed.

S/N	Seasoning	Colour	Texture	flavour	Taste
1	Beef meat	7	7	7	7
2	Garlic	7	7	8	8
3	Pole	6	6	7	7
4	African nutmeg	6	6	7	7
5	Maggi	9	8	9	9
6	Ohiha	7	6	7	7
7	pOziza	7	6	7	8
8	Locust bean	6	7	7	8
9	Ewuru	6	7	7	7
	Goat meat				
1	Ginger	7	7	7	7
2	Garlic	7	7	8	8
3	Pole	5	6	7	7
4	African nutmeg	5	6	7	7
5	Maggi	8	8	7	9
6	Ohiha	6	7	7	8
7	Oziza	7	7	7	8
8	Locust bean	7	6	7	8
9	Ewuru	6	6	8	7
	Chicken meat				
1	Ginger	7	7	7	7
2	Garlic	7	7	8	8
3	Pole	6	6	7	7
4	African nutmeg	6	6	7	7
5	Maggi	8	8	8	9
6	Ohiha	7	7	7	8
7	Oziza	7	6	7	8
8	Locust beans	7	6	8	7

Table 3: Overall acceptability of the meat samples

S/N	Seasoning	Cow	Goat	Chicken	Mean
1	Ginger	28	28	28	28
2	Garlic	30	30	30	30
3	Pole	26	25	26	25.3
4	African nutmeg	26	25	26	25.3
5	Maggi	33	32	37	34
6	Ohiha	29	28	27	28
7	Oziza	28	29	28	28.3
8	Locust been	28	28	28	28
9	Ewuru	28	27	27	27.3

Food spices (additives) are widely used these days as flavour enhancers. Sweeteners, leavening agents, nutrients etc. In Nigeria different spices are formal / used by different tribes. These spices have nutritional relevance and healing potentials (Ekpo and Jimmy, 2005). Akpanyung (2005) reported the extensive use of bouillon cubes they act as taste enhancers in Nigeria. Nnanyelugo (1999) ranked this bouillon cube among the topmost food fortifier in Nigeria Fayemi (1999), Parry (2000) and Solomon (2006) have reported in local spices, they concluded that these spices give humans some level of stimulation in the activity of the digestive tract. Adeyeye *et al* (2002) reported a natural food condiment (African locust bean) seeds as the most important natural food condiment in the entire savannah region of west and central Africa.

Meat is any flesh of an animal that is used for food. It is nutritious and highly attractive in appearance. There are various meat types, they have different chemical compositions (Soniran and Okubanjo 2002). Before consumption meats are cooked when cooked they tend to change colour, produce juices and texture changes. The time of cooking depends on the meat spices and so many other factors (McClenahan and Driskell 2002). The purpose of this study was to determine the effects of different local additives (garlic, ginger, pole, megnut, magi cube, ohiha, oziza and locust bean) on the sensory properties of meat (beef, goat and broiler) samples.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The meat (beef, goat and broiler) and seasonings (Table 1) used for this study were purchased from Erekesan market in Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria in August 2006. The seasonings were washed, cleaned, air dried, cut into pieces, ground in mortar and pestles and stored prior to analysis. The meat samples (900g) each were washed to remove dirt, cut into pieces totaling twenty seven (27) pieces ie 9 pieces for meat, 9 pieces for goat and 9 pieces broiler meat.

Cooking of samples

Into every pots, a piece of meat, 300cm³ of water and 6g each of the spices were added and cooked on Bunsen burner flame in Chemistry laboratory of Federal College of Agriculture, Akure campus. All samples were cooked until they were certified ready for consumption by an expert. Cooking time was between 30-45min depending on the type of meat sample.

Sensory Evaluation

Portions of the twenty, meat seven samples were each assessed by a 20-member panel. Panelists were at least 18years old and over. They were served pieces of samples and asked to evaluate the quality and acceptability by filling the questionnaire given to them. Samples were evaluated based on sensory attributes colour, texture, flavour, taste and overall acceptability on a 9-point hedonic scale of 1 to 9, with 9= like very much and 1= dislike very much. Scores were analyzed using analysis of variance.

Statistical Analysis

All statistical analyses were determined using SPSS for window 10.0. All analyzes were done in triplicate.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Sensory evaluation of the meat samples showed significant variations ($p>0.05$) in all the parameters nitrous. Even through the colour of most of the samples were slightly different, the results showed panelists overall acceptance of the colours of beef, goat and chicken meats cooked with magi cube (Table 2). The less preferred were those cooked with pole, nutmeg, ewuru and locust bean. As seen in table2, the texture of all the meat samples with oziza, ohiha, pole and nutmeg were less preferred. The most preferred was meats cooked with magi cube.

Magi cubes are taste enhancers when added to foods. The major ingredient is salt (Na Cl), monosodium glutamate (MSG), vegetable oil, starch and spices. MSG is a flavour enhance, classified under general recognized as safe (GRAS) by the US food and Drug Administration (Akpanyung 2005).

The release of more flavour components due to increased fat solubilization may have contributed to improved meat sample's flavour. Increase in meat flavour is caused by a greater activity of the Maillard reaction and associated reacting in valuing muscle protein, carbohydrates and lipids and their degradation products (Smoons *et al* 1995).

Spices are known to enhance and improve the flavour and colour of foods (Ekanem and Solomon 1997, Ekanem and Achirnewhu 1998). They vary in their effects in that the aroma and flavour principles in spices are based on the essential contained in them. It would be assumed that the oils present in magi cube and some of the spices may have produced some modification of the flavour, taste and colour thus making the meat samples generally accepted by the panelists.

The general overall acceptability (Table3) of the additives on the meats followed this sequence: magi>garlic>Oziza>Ohiha, ginger, locust been> ewuru>pole, nutmeg. This could be attributed to the special flavour, taste and colour the spices impacted on the meat samples.

CONCLUSION

From the analytical result, more of the panelists rated the effect of the flavour, colour, taste and texture as poor. It then showed that all of them have desirable sensory attributes (surface col.our, juiciness, tenderness, aromatic intensity and flavour intensity). Sensory evaluation in this study showed a high consumer preference for meats cooked with magi cube.

REFERENCE

- Adeyeye E.I, Ipinmoriti K.O and Oguntokin. 2002. Chemical composition and functional properties of the African locust bean (*parkia biglobosa*) seeds. *Pak.J. Sci. ind. Res.* 45(1): 29-33
- Akpanyung E.O. 2005. Proximate and mineral element composition of bouillon cubes produced in Nigeria. *Pak. J. Nutr.* 45(5): 327-329.
- Ekanem E.O and Solomon I.P. 1997. Chemical in the preservation and storage of selected animal food products. In *Application of chemistry* (I.O, Essien ed.), MEF publication Ltd. Uyo. Nigeria.
- Ekanem E.O and Achinewhu. S.C. 1998. Effects of spices application on microbiological quality and acceptance of West African clam meat processed by intermediate-moisture technology. *Proc. Silver Jubilee Anniversary conference.* O.Oduguwa, A.O Fanimu and O.A Osinowo (ed) Nig. Soc. Anim prod.
- Ekpo A.J and Jimmy E.O. 2005. Nutritional effect of spices from roasted chicken and beef meat consumption. *Pak. J. Nutr.* 4(6):428-430.
- Fayemi P.O. 1999. *Nigerian vegetables.* Hrinernann Education Book, Nigeria. Chapman and Hall Publication pp 124-126

- McClenahan J.M and Driskell J.A. 2002. Nutrient content and sensory characteristics of bison meat. The Board of regents of the University of Nebraska on behalf of the University of Nebraska-Lincoln Extension.
- Nieman D.C, Butterworth D.E and Nieman C.N. 1992. Nutrition. Revised ed. Wm. C. Brown Publishers, USA pp 301-303.
- Nnanyelugo D. 1999. Opportunities for food fortification technology in Nigeria. Vitamin Information Center, South Africa.
- Parry J. W. 2000. Spices-morphology, histology, chemistry. Vol II. Food Trade Ltd, London pp 176-180.
- Simmon S.I, Car T.R and Mckeitech J.K. 1985. Effect of internal temperature and thickness on palatability of pork. Loin chops. J. Food Sci 50:313-315.
- Solomon I.P. 2006. Consumers evaluation and acceptability of Lagomorphs processed with local spices. J. Res. Agric. 3(2):19-22.
- Soniran O.G and Okubanjo A.O 2002. Physico-chemical and sensory characteristics of pork loin roasted, cooked to three internal temperatures. Nig. J. Anim. Prod. 29(1):138-141.
- Wardlaw G.M. 1999. Perspective in nutrition. 4th ed. McGraw-Hill Companies USA. pp 520-522.

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Corresponding Author:

Eluyode O.S

Department of General Studies, Federal College of Agriculture, Akure 340001, Ondo State, Nigeria.